

AWARENESS AND UTILIZATION OF ELECTRONIC RESOURCES AMONG FINAL-YEAR GENERIC AND POST-RN STUDENTS IN NURSING INSTITUTES OF PESHAWAR PAKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: For the delivery of health services, an effective awareness about electronic information system is crucial as it can enhance services' quality, reduce costs and unintended consequences. It also ensures patient safety and strengthens the standard of healthcare services that can result from proper implementation. The Key role of Information Technology (IT) in the health sector is to extend geographic access, enhance client communication, improve disease diagnosis and treatment, improve data quality management, and protect client confidentiality.

Objective: To determine awareness and utilization of electronic resources among Final Year (Generic) and Post-RN BSN students in nursing Institutes of Peshawar.

Methodology: This analytical cross sectional study was carried out on the students of final year generic BSN and Post RN BSN in two public and two private sector nursing institutes from August 2023 to January 2024. Total sample size was calculated to be 270. Data was obtained on a pre-validated questionnaire after approval from ASRB of KMU using simple random sampling technique. Data was analyzed using SPSS V.24 and independent sample t-test was applied to see the mean difference in utilization of awareness and usage of electronic information resources.

Results: Major finding of the study revealed that nursing students were mostly (95.2%) aware and inclined towards the use of electronic information resources. They used electronic resources to make their class notes (56.3%) and enhancing their knowledge. However, the use of electronic journals was not prevalent (1.5%) among the nursing students. **Conclusion:** When compared the students of public and private nursing institutes, the students of public sector nursing institutes were more aware and used electronic information resources for their education. They also used electronic journals for various purposes more than the students of private sector institutes.

1. INTRODUCTION

All people agree that libraries are significant social institutions for the dissemination of knowledge and information (1), which can

improve performance of students' academics and the caliber of research conducted at academic institutions. Without the assistance

of a library and its services, no community, institution or organization can be deemed complete.

A library is defined as an organized collection of information resources in various formats that are created, stored, preserved, and made usable. A library, According to (2), is a specially constructed space where printed and other types of knowledge are gathered, arranged, and meticulously prepared in accordance with a predetermined plan before being made available for reading and consultation by people of all ages and interests. Every reputable university keeps a helpful library because it is one of the primary information sources for students, including nursing students (3).

Information resources are defined by (4), as "information bearing materials" that exist in both printed and electronic formats. Examples of these materials include video tapes/cassettes, microforms, computers, the internet/Email, CD-ROM databases, reports, newspapers and magazines, indexes, abstracts, journals, textbooks, magnetic disks, diskettes and so forth. Information resources, according to (5), are all the library resources or materials that the librarian uses to offer information services that satisfy nursing students' information demands. To increase the caliber of their research and raise their academic standing, nursing students must thus make the most of the information resources that are available to them. Furthermore, (6) contended that knowledge of the presence of a specific resource needed to satisfy one's information demands is essential for the efficient use of information resources. Any library's efficacy is dependent on the caliber of services provided, or how easily and readily available its information resources are to its patrons. In order to ensure user satisfaction, availability and use of books, journals etc. must be properly organized (7).

Globally, there is a connection between nursing practice, nursing education, and nursing research, and Pakistan is no exception. Barring any other circumstances, it is thought that receiving quality instruction in nursing during one's schooling improves standard practice, which is then supported by research. A gap appears if any of these are absent (8). An evaluation of nursing practices, procedures, policies, or curriculum, an assessment of

patients', staff members', or students' needs, and decisions about changing or continuing various nursing processes that advance the scientific knowledge in the nursing field are all part of the process of nursing research, also known as research in nursing (9). Nursing research, in the opinion of Basavanthappa B, can be used to find new information, enhance professional practice and education, and make efficient use of available resources (10).

Florence Nightingale's methods for providing care during and after the Crimean War served as the impetus for nursing study, when she meticulously documented her observations about the nursing care given to injured troops. These observations were then used to make required adjustments to nursing practice. This suggests that early nursing studies focused more on the observation of patient care. But until university nursing education gained popularity and these baccalaureate nurses employed all the resources at their disposal to pursue study on nursing as a profession and nursing education, nothing noteworthy was contributed to this by Nightingale's successors (9).

Academic libraries in nursing schools must have pertinent, high-quality information resources available in print and electronic formats in order to offer sufficient, high-quality services that will improve the caliber of students' nursing research. It makes sense that (11), thought that an academic library needed sufficient numbers of highly qualified information professionals as well as appropriate information resources in order to support teaching, learning, and research with effective information services. Concern has been expressed over the low caliber of research conducted by nursing students. The scenario's attendant consequences had a detrimental effect on the academic performance of both Basic and Post Basic Nursing Students at Benue State Schools of Nursing and Midwifery, Makurdi, and consequently threatened the goal and vision of nursing education with regard to high-quality research (14).

Based on preliminary observations, nursing students at the studied schools were so busy that they don't often visit the school libraries or use the library's information resources. It might raise the caliber and standard of their research, which is one of the requirements for being

granted a practicing license by the NMCN and ultimate certifying as a professional nurse. It becomes necessary to look into the information resources that are available in nursing and midwifery libraries and that nursing students could use to improve the quality of nursing research and increase operational effectiveness and efficiency. Thus, the purpose of this study is to discover how well public and private colleges, student nurses use information resources for nursing research.

2. Objective of the Study

To determine awareness and utilization of electronic resources among Final-Year Generic and Post-RN BSN students in nursing Institutes of Peshawar.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Internet and Electronic Resources

The largest network of information, communication, and technologies in the world is the Internet. It is utilized by nurses, doctors, and other healthcare providers (12-14). Nonetheless, other research indicated that health care providers underuse the Internet and ICT as information sources (15). Several more studies, such as those conducted by (16, 17), demonstrate that university students' use of the Internet for academic purposes is growing.

According to (18), a good education system should serve three purposes in De-schooling Society. These are: (i) giving everyone who wants to learn access to resources at any time in their lives; (ii) facilitating the ability of anyone who wants to share knowledge or other resources to find others who would like to learn from them; and (iii) creating opportunities for people who want to present an issue to the public to voice their opinions. The significance of local groups and networks in facilitating and maintaining learning was emphasized by Erkelens R et al. (19).

According to (20), researchers are increasingly using the web to retrieve information, and electronic materials will soon replace traditional libraries with digital libraries, eliminating the need for people to physically visit libraries to get the knowledge they require. In their study, (21) stated that clinical nurses and nursing students were most likely to rely on books and colleagues for medical information;

they also commonly mentioned personal digital assistants, electronic journals and books, and drug representatives as additional resources.

Online resources, such as CINAHL and PubMed, were utilized more frequently by nursing students than by clinical nurses to find health information, submit reports, and do database searches one to five times a week (21). In a study on students' web search habits, (22) found that two thirds of the students (67.5%) used the Internet every day, with 72.5% using it for research, 76.5% for education, 68% for entertainment, 18.5% for sports, and 6% for shopping.

According to (22), Google (97%), followed by Yahoo (72%), were the most popular search engine. The 183 first-year medical and nursing students at the University College Hospital of Ibadan, only 42.6% of the sample could use a computer, while 57.4% could not (23). Of those who could not, the majority (69.8%) said that their inability to do so was because they lacked access. According to the same study, e-mail was the most often used Internet service among students (76.4%), followed by student nurses (73.4%) and medical students (81.3%). The results of a study by (24) showed that over half of the sample had never sent or received emails from their professors, 56.5% had never posted ideas online, and 94.6% had never submitted files to the Internet. In a research by (25) on the sources of information used by students, 56% and 85% of the material came from the internet and libraries, respectively.

3.2 Awareness of E-Resources among Students

The proliferation of electronic resources has made it necessary for library patrons to possess a solid understanding of the resources' accessibility and availability. The majority of universities worldwide are making significant investments in e-resources to meet their demands for teaching, learning, and research (26, 27). These colleges have made significant investments in e-resources, but it is unclear how they will be used in practice. According to a study (28), knowing where to find electronic resources and how to use them effectively are the only prerequisites for using them effectively (29). Some of the reasons for underusing e-resources are low knowledge (28), poor search

skills, and heavy reliance on general search engines (27). As a result, understanding becomes crucial to students in higher education institutions using e-resources effectively.

Research on students' knowledge of electronic resources has been widely carried out at a variety of international higher education institutions (30, 31). The research does, however, indicate that there are instances in which students' awareness and use of the accessible e-resources are out of sync. (27) Outlined three interconnected aspects of knowledge and application of e-resources. It's possible that library patrons use and are aware of the electronic resources offered. Sometimes, people who use libraries may also be aware of the electronic resources available to them, but they may not take advantage of them because they are unaware of these (27).

For instance, (32) discovered that the majority of graduate students were not aware of particular journal features, which prevented them from fully utilizing e-resources in their research (33). Nisha F and Ali N (34) discovered in their study that library patrons were knowledgeable about the electronic resources at their disposal and made good use of them for their academic and research endeavors. Additionally, according to (35), library patrons at the University of Ghana Medical School's College of Health Sciences were not aware of the availability of e-resources through the Health Inter-Network Access to Research Initiative (HINARI) program. As a result, their only resource for full-text journal articles was PUBMED. In a similar vein, the University of Lagos study that looked at how medical students used the Medline database found that students were not aware of e-resources, which led to poor Medline database usage.

3.3 Usage of E-Resources by Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students

Because of its recentness and extensive content, e-resources have been used more frequently in higher education institutions in recent years. A number of studies have been carried out to determine the effectiveness with which the subscribed e-resources are being used. Infrastructure, search proficiency, awareness, and lack of training are a few examples of

elements that have been identified as influencing e-resource adoption. For instance, (36) looked into how University of Namibia nursing students used electronic resources. According to the study's findings, 86.4% of the students did not utilize the electronic resources that were offered to them because students were unaware of their availability.

Comparably, 92% of respondents in a study (37) on the University of Cape Coast's use of e-resources in Ghana acknowledged the presence of e-resources at their university. It's interesting to see that respondents were unaware that the university library had a subscription to those electronic services. Furthermore, a study (31) discovered that frequent power outages and sluggish internet connection are two prevalent issues that hinder the efficient use of e-resources.

Along these same lines, a number of research on Tanzanian higher education institutions' students' use and access to e-resources have been carried out. For instance, (38) looked into how agricultural researchers and extension personnel used online resources. These researchers discovered that the use of electronic resources from well-known agricultural databases was minimal. Low accessibility and utilization of e-resources were caused by a number of factors, including inadequate ICT infrastructure, insufficient funding for e-resource subscriptions, and a lack of information literacy training. Conversely, (39) examined how Tanzanian College of Business Education students used electronic resources. The results showed that the majority of students were not utilizing e-resources because they were unaware that the school had e-resources available. The researcher found that the use of connected computers and poor search abilities had an impact on e-resource utilization.

3.4 Usage of Electronic Resources by Health Sciences Students

In the digital age, electronic information resources are becoming a vital component of library collections and are necessary for research, teaching, and learning activities. A number of studies have recently evaluated students' understanding and usage of electronic information resources (EIR) in light of the

inherent benefits of EIR. In a study on the use and effects of electronic resources at the Institute of Technology, Delhi, (40) discovered that user awareness is the reason for the rise in the use of electronic journals.

In his investigation of Bangalore's medical and management colleges, (41) discovered that the students there are accustomed to using the internet and are aware of e-resources. However, due to a lack of awareness, (42) said that the majority of library patrons are ignorant of the high caliber and diversity of information found in academic libraries. In a university in a poor nation, (43) carried out a study to find out how satisfied students were with the online resources they could access through subscription. As a result, a large number of students did not use the resources that the institution had paid for.

According to a study by (44), insufficient online database availability, a lack of formal internet literacy training, sluggish bandwidth, and slow servers were the main causes of students' inadequate use of digital information resources. Ineffective marketing strategies, inadequate training, lack of awareness, poor infrastructure, low access to and use of free online resources (45, 46), staff uncooperativeness, and password loss are other factors linked to low use of electronic resources among undergraduates in prior studies (47-49).

3.5 Usage of Electronic Resources by Nursing Students

Academic libraries, such as those at nursing and midwifery schools, offer knowledge and information resources for research, teaching, and learning in this area. Additionally, books are the primary information resource in the library and the most widely used and accessible information resource for research. Additionally, (50) found that the majority of students use government publications, dictionaries, handbooks, bibliographies, encyclopedias, projects, theses, and dissertations, library staff, conference proceedings, technical reports, newspapers, magazines, pamphlets / posters, textbooks, journals, seminars / symposia, bulletins / newsletters, and academic libraries on a daily basis for research and academic purposes.

Print materials are the primary information resources used by nursing students who are frequent library users, according to (3) study on the use of information resources by student nurses. The study also showed that, to a large degree, books, journals, encyclopedias, dictionaries, and directories are the information resources that nurses utilize the most frequently. In terms of academic libraries, student satisfaction with the use of information resources in the library is a crucial factor. This is due to the fact that a library's user base is its most crucial element.

Student nurses are content with the library information resources available at their institution, according to (51) study, A Survey on the Use of Library Information Resources by Students of Ondo State School of Nursing Akure. Nursing students face several obstacles while attempting to access information resources, such as time constraints, library location, and unfriendly library staff. Similar to this, (51) found that obstacles preventing student nurses at Ondo State School of Nursing Akure from using information resources were a lack of time, inadequate knowledge on how to utilize them effectively, and a lack of internet access. Another study (52) reported the degree of satisfaction with the library resources in relation to the use of information resources. According to their study, pupils are really happy using the library's information resources.

4. Hypothesis

- **H₀:** There is no statistical mean difference in the awareness and utilization of electronic resources between the students of GBSN and Post-RN BSN
- **H₁:** There is a statistical mean difference in the awareness and utilization of electronic resources between the students of GBSN and Post-RN BSN

5. Research Methodology

An analytical cross sectional (correlational) study design was used. This study was conducted in public (KMU Institute of Nursing Sciences, Postgraduate Nursing College) and private (RMI School of Nursing, Northwest Institute of Health Sciences) nursing institutes of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan.

Study duration was six months from October, 2023 to March, 2024. Enrolled final year students of Generic BSN and Post RN BSN were included in the study. Those final year GBSN and Post-RN BSN students who were not willing to participate or absent on the day of data collection were excluded from the study. The sample size calculator RaoSoft yielded a sample 270 (i.e. 166 from generic BSN and 103 from Post-RN BSN,) with a 0.95 confidence level, margin of error = 0.05, response distribution of 50% and considering the population size of GBSN as 290 and Post-RN BSN as 140. Simple random sampling technique was used in this study.

Approval was obtained from the graduation committees of INS, AS and RB of KMU. Permission was obtained from the heads of the related institutions for data collection. A written, informed consent was obtained from the participants. A pre-validated (105) questionnaire was provided to the nursing students, and their data was collected in the

form of filled-out questionnaires. Analysis of the data was done through SPSS V.24. Sample mean and standard deviation was measured for continuous variables like time spent in library, how often visit to library, and percentages were computed for qualitative variables like preference of information etc. Independent samples T-test was applied to see the mean difference in utilization and awareness of IT resources.

6. Results

6.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

The results in table no. 1 shows that 68 (25.2%) students participated from KMU Institute of Nursing Sciences, 67 (24.8%) from Postgraduate Nursing College, 68 (25.2%) from RMI School of Nursing and 67 (24.8%) from North West College of Nursing. Similarly, out of total 270 participants 166 (61.5%) were BS Nursing students and 104 (38.5%) were Post RN BSN students.

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

S. No.	Name of the Institute	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1.	KMU Institute of Nursing Sciences	68	25.2
2.	Postgraduate Nursing College	67	24.8
3.	RMI School of Nursing	68	25.2
4.	North West College of Nursing	67	24.8
Name of the Degree Program			
1.	BS Nursing	166	61.5
2.	Post RN BSN	104	38.5
Semester			
1.	4 th Post RN BSN	104	38.5
2.	7 th BS Nursing	24	8.9
3.	8 th BS Nursing	142	52.6
Gender			
1.	Male	148	54.8
2.	Female	122	45.2
Total		270	100

6.2 Awareness and use of library resources

Table 2 shows that 200 (74.1%) students visited library while 70 (25.9%) gave negative response. Similarly 44 (16.3%) student visited library on daily basis, 117 (43.3%) on weekly basis, 20 (7.4%) on monthly basis, 80 (29.6%)

occasionally and only 9 (3.3%) visited the library fortnightly. Out of total 270, 223

(82.6%) students were aware of the library resources while 47 (17.4%) were unaware. Moreover, 38 (14.1%) students stated that they spend not more than 30 minutes in library, 84

(31.1%) less than 1 hour, 59 (21.9%) one to 2 hours, 16 (5.9%) two to three hours, 8 (3.0%)

more than 3 hours and 65 (24.1%) students not responded.

Table 1 Awareness and use of library resources 1

S. No.	Do you visit the library?	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1.	Yes	200	74.1
2.	No	70	25.9
How often do you visit library?			
1.	Daily	44	16.3
2.	Weekly	117	43.3
3.	Monthly	20	7.4
4.	Occasionally	80	29.6
5.	Fortnightly	9	3.3
Are you aware of library resources?			
1.	Yes	223	82.6
2.	No	47	17.4
How much time do you spend in library on daily basis?			
1.	Not more than 30 Min	38	14.1
2.	Less than 1 Hour	84	31.1
3.	1-2 Hours	59	21.9
4.	2-3 Hours	16	5.9
5.	More than 3 Hours	8	3.0
6.	Not Responded	65	24.1

Table 3 shows the preferences and use of information resources by participants. Printed resources was the preference of 75 (27.8%) students, Electronic resources by 56 (20.7%) students and 139 (51.5%) preferred both type of resources. Similarly 12 (4.4%) student stated that information resources are essential, 159 (58.9%) stated very important, 89 (33.0%)

stated important while 10 (3.7%) stated that these are somewhat important. In the same way students were asked regarding the use of search engines, 250 (92.6%) replied positive and 20 (7.4%) replied negative. Google was used by 248 (91.9%) students as search engine and 22 (8.1%) used Google scholar.

Table 2 Awareness and use of library resources 2

S. No.	Please mention your preference of the information format?	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1.	Printed Resources	75	27.8
2.	Electronic Resources	56	20.7
3.	Both	139	51.5
How much these resources are important?			
1.	Essential	12	4.4
2.	Very Important	159	58.9
3.	Important	89	33.0
4.	Somewhat Important	10	3.7
Do you use search engines to find information?			
1.	Yes	250	92.6
2.	No	20	7.4
If yes, Please indicate which ones you mostly use for search information?			
1.	Google	248	91.9
2.	Google Scholar	22	8.1
3.	PubMed	0	0

4.	Medlin	0	0
5.	Any Other	0	0

6.3 Awareness and use of Electronic Resources

Table 4 states that 259 (95.9%) participants were aware of the electronic resources while 11 (4.1%) were unaware. 257 (95.2%) used electronic resources and 13 (4.8%) didn't use it. When they were asked about where they used electronic resources, 42 (15.6%) stated as Library, 9 (3.3%) accessed in department, 152 (56.3%) accessed at hostel, 54 (20.0%) accessed at home and 13 (4.8%) not responded. Similarly, 173 (64.1%) students used the electronic resources on daily basis, 82 (30.4%)

on weekly basis, 4 (1.5%) on monthly basis and 11 (4.1%) never used it. The type of electronic resource used by study participants was E-Book by 58 (21.5%), E-Journal by 4 (1.5%), E-Newspaper by 114 (42.2%), E-Magazine by 38 (14.1%), Multimedia Product by 49 (18.1%) and any Other by 7 (2.6%) students. In the same way 12 (4.4%) students used the electronic resources for research, 152 (56.3%) for class notes, 6 (2.2%) for project work, 34 (12.6%) for lectures and 66 (24.4%) used it for other purposes.

Table 3 Awareness and use of Electronic Resources

S. No.	Are you aware of electronic resources?	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1.	Yes	259	95.9
2.	No	11	4.1
Do you use electronic resources?			
1.	Yes	257	95.2
2.	No	13	4.8
If 'Yes 'where do you access electronic resources?			
1.	Library	42	15.6
2.	Department	9	3.3
3.	Hostel	152	56.3
4.	Home	54	20.0
5.	Not Responded	13	4.8
How often do you use electronic resources?			
1.	Daily	173	64.1
2.	Weekly	82	30.4
3.	Monthly	4	1.5
4.	Never	11	4.1
What types of electronic resources do you mostly use?			
1.	E-Book	58	21.5
2.	E-Journal	4	1.5
3.	E-Newspaper	114	42.2
4.	E-Magazine	38	14.1
5.	Multimedia Product	49	18.1
6.	Any Other	7	2.6
For what purpose do you use electronic information?			
1.	For Research	12	4.4
2.	For Class Notes	152	56.3
3.	For Project Work	6	2.2
4.	For Lecture	34	12.6
5.	Any Other	66	24.4

6.4 Awareness and use of Electronic Journals

Table 5 shows that 131 (48.5%) participants used electronic journals while 139 (51.5%) did not use. Similarly 10 (3.7%) use the electronic journals to write articles, 108 (40.0%) to prepare presentations / notes, 23 (8.5%) for

updating knowledge and 129 (47.8%) did not responded. Features of the electronic journals used by student were table of contents 13 (4.8%), Abstract 22 (8.1%), Article Reference 39 (14.4%), Full Text 88 (32.6%) and 108 (40.0%) did not respond.

Table 4 Awareness and use of Electronic Journals

S. No.	Do you use electronic journals?	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1.	Yes	131	48.5
2.	No	139	51.5
For what purpose do you use electronic journals?			
1.	To write articles	10	3.7
2.	To prepare presentations/notes	108	40.0
3.	For updating knowledge	23	8.5
4.	Not Responded	129	47.8
Which Features of the electronic journals do you use?			
1.	Table of Contents	13	4.8
2.	Abstract	22	8.1
3.	Article Reference	39	14.4
4.	Full Text	88	32.6
5.	Not Responded	108	40.0

6.5 Comparison of the Means by Independent sample t-test

Table 6 shows that there was a significant association (P-Value = 0.001) between public and private nursing institutes while visiting library with majority of the public sector nursing institutes students visited library i. e. 113 (56.5%) with the mean score of 0.84 (± 0.37). Table 7 also shows that there was a significant association (P-Value = 0.032) between public and private nursing institutes regarding frequency of visit to library with

majority of the public sector nursing institute students visited library i. e. 28 (63.6%) with mean score of 2.55 (± 1.14). Table 8 shows that awareness of library resources was maximum in public sector nursing institutes students i.e. 130 (58.3%) with mean score of 0.96 (± 0.19). Table 9 shows that majority of the public sector nursing institutes students visited library on daily basis for more than 3 hours i.e. 8 (100%) and 2-3 hours i.e. 12 (75.0%) with mean score of 2.63 (± 1.29).

Table 5 Visit to the library

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Yes	113 (56.5%)	87 (43.5%)
No	22 (31.4%)	48 (68.6%)
Mean	0.84	0.64
Std. Deviation	0.37	0.48
P-Value	0.001	

Table 6 Frequency of Visit to Library

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Daily	28 (63.6%)	16 (36.4%)
Weekly	56 (47.9%)	61 (52.1%)
Monthly	18 (90.0%)	2 (10.0%)
Fortnightly	28 (35.0%)	52 (65.0%)
Occasionally	5 (56.6%)	4 (44.4%)
Mean	2.55	2.24
Std. Deviation	1.14	1.18
P-Value	0.032	

Table 7 Awareness of Library Resources

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Yes	130 (58.3%)	93 (41.7%)
No	5 (10.6%)	42 (89.4%)
Mean	0.96	0.69
Std. Deviation	0.19	0.46
P-Value	0.001	

Table 8 Time spent in library on daily basis

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Not more than 30 Min	25 (65.8%)	13 (34.2%)
Less than 1 Hour	33 (39.3%)	51 (60.7%)
1-2 Hours	9 (15.3%)	50 (84.7%)
2-3 Hours	12 (75.0%)	4 (25.0%)
More than 3 Hours	8 (100%)	0 (0%)
Mean	2.63	2.62
Std. Deviation	1.29	0.73
P-Value	0.924	

Table 10 shows that there was a significant association (P-Value = 0.001) between public and private nursing institutes regarding preference of information format with majority of the public sector nursing institutes students preferred Electronic Resources i. e. 48 (85.7%) with the mean score of 2.41 (± 0.69). Similarly, table 11 shows that there was a significant

association (P-Value = 0.001) between public and private nursing institutes regarding Importance of Electronic Resources with majority of the public sector nursing institutes students considered Electronic Resources as “Very Important” i. e. 99 (62.3%) with the mean score of 1.78 (± 0.47).

Table 9 Preference of the information format

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Printed Resources	16 (21.3%)	59 (78.7%)
Electronic Resources	48 (85.7%)	8 (14.3%)
Both	71 (51.1%)	68 (48.9%)
Mean	2.41	2.07
Std. Deviation	0.69	0.97
P-Value	0.001	

Table 10 Importance of Electronic Resources

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Essential	3 (25.0%)	9 (75.0%)
Very Important	99 (62.3%)	60 (37.7%)
Important	33 (37.1%)	56 (62.9%)
Somewhat Important	0 (0 %)	10 (100%)
Mean	1.78	1.50
Std. Deviation	0.47	0.73
P-Value	0.001	

Table 12 shows that there was not a significant association (P-Value = 0.304) between public and private nursing institutes regarding use of search engines to find information with majority of the public sector nursing institutes students use search engines i. e. 129 (50.8%) with the mean score of 0.96 (± 0.21). Similarly, table no. 13 shows that there was not a

significant association (P-Value = 0.354) between public and private nursing institutes regarding search engines mostly use for search information with majority of the private sector nursing institutes students used Google i. e. 127 (50.8%) with the mean score of 0.94 (± 0.24).

Table 11 Use of search engines to find information

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Yes	129 (50.8%)	125 (49.2%)
No	6 (37.5%)	10 (62.5%)
Mean	0.96	0.93
Std. Deviation	0.21	0.26
P-Value	0.304	

Table 12 Use of search engines mostly use for search information

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Google	123 (49.2%)	127 (50.8%)
Google Scholar	12 (60.0%)	8 (40.0%)
Mean	0.91	0.94
Std. Deviation	0.29	0.24
P-Value	0.354	

Table 14 shows that there was not a significant association (P-Value = 0.125) between public and private nursing institutes regarding awareness of Electronic Resources with majority of the public sector nursing institutes students aware of electronic resources i. e. 132 (51.0%) with the mean score of 0.98 (± 0.15). Table 15 shows that 132 (51.4%) students of public sector nursing institutes used electronic resources with mean score of 0.98 (± 0.15). Table 16 shows that majority of the public sector nursing institutes students used electronic resources in Hostel i. e. 66 (48.1%)

with mean score of 1.27 (± 1.03). Similarly, table 17 shows that majority of the public sector nursing institutes students used electronic resources daily i. e. 93 (53.8%) with mean score of 2.66 (± 0.54). Table 18 shows that majority of the public sector nursing institutes students used electronic resources with the mean score of 3.07 (± 1.62). Table 19 shows that majority of the public sector nursing institutes students used electronic resources for different purposes e.g. research work, assignments etc. with the mean score of 2.27 (± 1.17).

Table 13 Awareness of Electronic Resources

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Yes	132 (51.0%)	127 (49.0%)
No	3 (27.3%)	8 (72.7%)
Mean	0.98	0.94
Std. Deviation	0.15	0.24
P-Value	0.125	

Table 14 Use of Electronic Resources

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Yes	132 (51.4%)	125 (48.6%)
No	3 (23.1%)	10 (76.9%)
Mean	0.98	0.93
Std. Deviation	0.15	0.26
P-Value	0.047	

Table 15 Location of the use of Electronic Resources

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Library	27 (64.3%)	15 (35.7%)
Department	6 (66.7%)	3 (33.3%)
Hostel	66 (48.1%)	28 (51.9%)
Home	26 (48.1%)	28 (51.9%)
Mean	1.27	1.04
Std. Deviation	1.03	0.83
P-Value	0.045	

Table 16 Frequency of the use of Electronic Resources

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Daily	93 (53.8%)	80 (46.2%)
Weekly	38 (46.3%)	44 (53.7%)
Monthly	4 (28.6%)	10 (71.4%)
Never	0 (0 %)	1 (100%)
Mean	2.66	2.50
Std. Deviation	0.54	0.70
P-Value	0.033	

Table 17 Type of Electronic Resources mostly used

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
E-Book	36 (62.1%)	22 (37.9%)
E-Journal	4 (100%)	0 (0%)
E-Newspaper	57 (50.0%)	57 (50.0%)
E-Magazine	31 (81.6%)	7 (18.4 %)
Multimedia Product	7 (14.3%)	42 (85.7 %)
Any Other	0 (0 %)	7 (100 %)
Mean	3.07	1.41
Std. Deviation	1.62	2.81
P-Value	0.001	

Table 18 Purpose of the use of Electronic Resources

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
For Research	6 (50.0%)	6 (50.0%)
For Class Notes	83 (54.6%)	69 (45.4%)
For Project Work	0 (0%)	6 (100%)
For Lecture	33 (97.1%)	1 (2.9 %)
Any Other	13 (19.7 %)	53 (80.3 %)
Mean	2.27	1.81
Std. Deviation	1.17	1.50
P-Value	0.005	

Table 20 shows that there was not a significant association (P-Value > 0.05) for majority of the electronic databases between public and private

nursing institutes, however, mean scores for use of all the electronic databases were high for public nursing institutes.

Table 19 Mean use of the Electronic Databases

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes	P-Value
PubMed	2.63 (±0.76)	0.92 (±1.27)	0.001
Springer Link	1.84 (±1.84)	1.69 (±1.69)	0.558
Medline Plus	2.63 (±2.63)	1.69 (±1.69)	0.001
Science Direct	2.53 (±2.53)	1.92 (±1.92)	0.057
BMJ	1.60 (±1.60)	1.46 (±1.46)	0.659
Wiley-Blackwell Journal	1.68 (±1.68)	1.30 (±1.30)	0.220
Free Medical Journal	1.89 (±1.89)	1.69 (±1.69)	0.514
Royal College of Physicians	2.00 (±2.00)	1.92 (±1.92)	0.843
Emerald	2.37 (±2.37)	1.46 (±1.46)	0.004
JAMA	1.84 (±1.84)	1.30 (±1.30)	0.132
Any other	5.00 (±5.00)	2.00 (±2.00)	0.503

Table 21 shows that there was not a significant association (P-Value = 0.396) between public and private nursing institutes regarding use of electronic journals with majority of the public sector nursing institutes students used electronic journals i. e. 69 (52.7%) with the

mean score of 0.51 (±0.50). Similarly, table 22 shows that the mean score for purpose of electronic journals use was high for public sector nursing institutes students i. e. 1.94 (±0.59).

Table 20 Use of Electronic Journals

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
Yes	69 (52.7%)	62 (47.3%)
No	66 (47.5%)	73 (52.5%)
Mean	0.51	0.46
Std. Deviation	0.50	0.50
P-Value	0.396	

Table 21 Purpose of the use of Electronic Journals

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes
To write articles	10 (100%)	0 (0%)
To prepare presentations/notes	45 (41.7%)	63 (58.3%)
For updating knowledge	14 (60.9%)	9 (39.1%)
Mean	1.94	1.87
Std. Deviation	0.59	0.33
P-Value	0.406	

Table 23 shows that there was not a significant association (P-Value > 0.05) for majority of the problems faced while using electronic information resources between public and

private nursing institutes, however, mean scores for problems faced while using electronic information resources were high for public nursing institutes.

Table 22 Problems faced while using Electronic Information Resources with Std. Deviation

Institute	Public Sector Nursing Institutes	Private Sector Nursing Institutes	P-Value
Unavailability of required materials	2.65 (±1.70)	2.21 (±0.76)	0.096
Lack of technical support	2.13 (±1.62)	2.25 (±0.54)	0.596
Lack of training	2.64 (±1.73)	2.28 (±0.80)	0.187
Non Availability of Full Text Journal	3.19 (±0.74)	2.53 (±1.12)	0.014
lack of adequate number of computers	3.19 (±1.00)	2.34 (±0.66)	0.001
less speed of the connectivity	3.50 (±0.51)	2.82 (±1.10)	0.003
frequently power failure	2.78 (±1.16)	1.41 (±0.86)	0.341
Any Other	0 (±0)	0 (±0)	

7. Discussion

According to this study male participants were dominant and equal number of students were selected from public and private nursing institutes. Visit to library was prevalent among participants of the nursing institutes, however, the students mostly visited the library on weekly basis. It shows that there are more people in the library who do not use electronic information resources. This result supports the findings of (53) and (54) which showed that the frequency of use was pitifully low despite the availability of a large variety of resources. The inference is that the main obstacles to nursing institution students using electronic information resources were a lack of computers

and other resources. These results validated the outcomes of earlier researches (44, 55).

This study instigates that majority (82.6%) of the nursing students were aware of the library resources, however, they spent less than 1 hour in library. More than half of the students were of the opinion that these resources are very important for learning. Google was top search engines use by these students. The possible justification may be that Google is the easiest way to search any information and available on every device easily.

The finding that 95.9 % of respondents were aware of the electronic resources, concurred with the findings by (34, 37, 44), that recorded over 90% awareness of the electronic resources

in their institutions. This also indicates that the students got benefited with the library information literacy programs organized periodically to make them aware of the available resources. These results is contradictory to those of (37, 53) and other studies in which percentage of awareness is usually reported lower. This further demonstrates the need for greater efforts to encourage all students to use these crucial tools. Ineffective use of technological resources in the modern world may be caused by both a lack of awareness and the skills required to use them.

The findings of this study indicates that the nursing students mostly used electronic resources in Hostel and also majority of them used on daily basis. This agrees with (53) and (54). It also buttressed the assertion by (56) that information availability may not necessarily translate to use. E-Newspaper was the top used electronic resource. Most of the students used electronic resources for class notes. The findings corroborate that of (47, 49, 53) who individually reported high level of awareness of electronic information resources among the undergraduates in tertiary institutions. More than half of the Participants of this study were not aware of the electronic journals available at the resource center of University. Librarians should be extremely concerned about this given the significant costs associated with subscribing to electronic resources. The finding however negates that of (57) who demonstrated that many students were aware of electronic journals.

Therefore, it is possible to infer from the findings that students mostly used electronic information resources for the objectives of discovering pertinent material, conducting research, and finishing tasks. This suggests that pupils understood the value of electronic resources for information in academic works. The aforementioned results align with the research conducted by (58) which confirmed that electronic information resources foster academic research. The results also align with the research of (59), who found that students use EIR for a variety of tasks, such as researching, writing papers, and staying up to date on information.

Major objective of this study included to compare the use of electronic information

resources among public and private sector nursing institutes. The results of current study revealed that more than half of the students of public sector nursing institutes visited the Library. Similarly, major portion of the students of public sector nursing institutes visited the library on daily basis. Awareness of library resources and time spent in library was also high among public sector nursing institutes students. This shows the inclination of public sector nursing institutes students toward usage of library resources in comparison to the students of private sector nursing institutes.

Current study also instigates the good awareness and use of electronic information resources by the student so of public sector nursing institutes in comparison to private sector nursing institutes. The use of electronic information resources on daily basis was high among students of public sector nursing institutes. These findings are in line with the previous studies of (60, 61) and (62). Similarly, the use of electronic journals was also high among students of public sector nursing institutes. Major problem faced by the students of public sector nursing institutes while using electronic information resources was less speed of the internet connectivity. This is an area of concern by the students, the public sector nursing institutes must focus on and upgrade the resources hindering the use of electronic information resources.

8. Conclusions

This study was aimed to determine awareness and utilization of electronic resources among Final-Year (Generic) and Post-RN BSN students in nursing Institutes of Peshawar. Major finding of the study revealed that nursing students were mostly aware and inclined towards the use of electronic information resources. They used electronic resources to make their class notes and updating their knowledge. However, the use of electronic journals was not prevalent among the nursing students. When compared the students of public and private nursing institutes, the students of public sector nursing institutes were more aware and used electronic information resources for their education. They also used electronic journals for various purpose more than the students at private sector institutes.

9. Limitations

- Due to lack of resources and time constraints, this study was conducted in Peshawar only. More effective and valuable results could be obtained if the same could be expanded to the other areas of Pakistan where people are living in different living standards.
- We used a questionnaire which was close ended, there exist other questionnaires to be tested in the current study settings and qualitative method may also be used for the purpose.
- It was a cross sectional study, so it cannot provide casual associations.

10. Recommendations

- The topic of awareness and utilization of electronic resources among nursing students is very relevant in Pakistani society, however it is under-researched.
- After this study, an appreciation for the use of electronic resources is further developed by the researcher.
- We established a gap for further studies which involves in-depth investigation of the affects for external and internal aspects, in addition to the systemic and protective aspects.
- There is much scope of further research on the topic using different sample type and study area.

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